

Research

Preparation of monophasic YAG raw material by multi-stage process

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Abstract

The paper deals with the study of the features of the process of YAG phase formation via the Solid-State Reaction (SSR) method according to the proposed multi-stage scheme, including three stages of various mechanical and thermal processing (pre-milling in a ball mill for 24, 48 and 72 h, as well as firing at 1150 °C, 1250 °C, and 1450 °C with intermediate grinding step). The commercial micrometer-sized Y_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 powders were used as starting materials. The phase transformation was monitored by the X-ray diffraction in each synthesis stage. The microstructure and elemental distribution of samples were studied by scanning electron microscopy and energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry. During the work, we found the dual effects of partially reacted mixture grinding, which can accelerate or slow down the synthesis rate depending on the YAG content in the preceding stage. We have proposed a simple model including the concept of “critical YAG concentration”. When the lower limit of this parameter (over 60 %) is reached, grinding has a negative effect on the further course of the SSR. Carrying out the synthesis according to a three-stage scheme makes it possible to obtain a product with a YAG content above 90 %, regardless of the pre-milling time, and the use of a two-stage synthesis scheme provides a monophasic raw material (99 % of YAG) suitable for further single crystals growth. The increased efficiency of the multi-stage YAG synthesis scheme was demonstrated in comparison with the conventional one-stage obtaining process that yielded only up to 60% of the target phase in the temperature range up to 1500 °C.

Highlights

- Development of a technique for obtaining monophasic $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ by solid-state synthesis under acceptable conditions.
- Knowledge of the conditions for thermal and mechanical treatment of Y_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 oxide mixture allow obtaining monophasic garnet raw material at 1450 °C.
- The proposed technique will be useful in various fields of YAG powders application and, in particular, in the crystal growth research.

Keywords Yttrium–aluminium garnet (YAG) · Solid-state reaction (SSR) · Micrometer-sized powders · Multi-stage synthesis process

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1 Introduction

Crystallization processes of various materials from a melt are currently widely used, particularly Yttrium Aluminum Garnet ($Y_3Al_5O_{12}$, YAG) single crystals and Directionally Solidified Eutectic (DSE) ceramic [1–3]. $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ crystals are one of the most developed materials as laser hosts and phosphors due to their optical properties and uniqueness when doped with rare-earth cations [4–6]. DSE ceramics of binary (Al_2O_3 - $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ (YAG) and ternary (Al_2O_3 -YAG- ZrO_2) eutectics add new potentialities to the advantages of sintered ceramics: a higher strength, which is almost constant up to temperatures close to their melting point and higher creep resistance [7]. Features of the obtaining melts in the Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 system causing deviations from stoichiometry or crystallization of metastable phases were studied in publications [8, 9]. Overheating the melt in the Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 system above a temperature of 2000 °C in a large field of compositions on both the Y_2O_3 -poor side and the Y_2O_3 -rich side of YAG leads to a metastable solidification path. These results confirm the existence of problems associated with the interpretation of the grown crystals characteristics. This effect is most pronounced for growing crystals from the melt by Heat Exchange Method (HEM) [10, 11], Temperature Gradient Technique (TGT) [12–14], and Horizontal Directional Solidification (HDS) [15, 16] methods, which are distinguishing by weak convective mixing of the melt and, accordingly, the need for its homogenization. The authors [11, 17] note the necessity to use monophasic raw materials to obtain good-quality YAG crystals.

Two main synthesis methods can be used for the YAG powder preparation as raw materials for the crystal growth: co-precipitation from solutions and the solid-state reaction method, which can be used for the YAG powder preparation as raw materials for the crystal growth [18–20]. Relative to the solution method, SSR has advantages in the process scalability and lower cost though requiring a higher temperature for the YAG phase formation up to 1600 °C [21]. The fine grain size and the grain sizes distribution of the initial powders, along with the method of their mixing, grinding, and compacting, are the main factors determining the main parameters of the synthesis by the SSR method, such as the maximum annealing temperature and the duration of the process [22]. The synthesis of YAG in the Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 system via the SSR method is complicated by the formation of the intermediate compounds of $Y_4Al_2O_9$ (YAM) and $YAlO_3$ (YAP). This fact changes the kinetics of the overall reaction resulting in prolonged heating or the necessity to use a higher temperature. In addition, the synthesized powders are contaminated with Al_2O_3 and YAP residue [23]. For example, the usage of commercial micrometer-sized initial powders in the synthesis by SSR method, a temperature of 1350 °C for 40 h was not sufficient for achieving YAG single phase [24]. Proposed by authors [11, 17] process for the preparation of single-phase YAG raw material consisted of 72-h grinding in a ball mill of the commercial powders Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 mixture, isostatic pressing at 250 MPa, and 3-h final calcination at a temperature of 1650 °C.

It is known, as the reaction begins, agglomerates like concentric shells of YAM, YAP, and YAG will form around the Y_2O_3 particles, and Al^{+3} ions will thus diffuse through the YAG and intermediate YAP and YAM to reach the remaining Y_2O_3 [25]. In the course of a solid–solid reaction, due to its heterogeneous nature, various reaction steps take place, such as nucleation, transport of a substance along phase boundaries, and the most significantly, the transport of matter across a solid–solid phase boundary. In the initial stage of SSR, a linear rate law should have been expected, since the diffusion resistance of newly formed product thin layers may be negligible compared to the resistance of the layers forming at later stages [26]. Thus, the SSR rate is determined by faster surface and slower diffusion mechanisms, and the last one is the limitation stage of the process. Periodically cooling and grinding the partially reacted powders often greatly accelerates SSR: grinding maintains a high surface area, while bringing new surfaces into contacts [27], and creating conditions for surface reactions mechanism. Accordingly, the SSR rate could be increased, and the firing temperature during the complete final product formation might be decreased by introducing the intermediate stages into YAG obtaining technological scheme.

The aim of this study is the evaluation of the efficiency of multi-stage YAG synthesis from commercially available micrometer-sized α - Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 powders to obtain a monophasic raw material for growing YAG single crystals from the melt using simple equipment and firing at temperatures below 1500 °C. In other words, the goal of the study is the development of an inexpensive synthesis process that could be easily adapted to the production environment.

Fig. 1 The three-stage synthesis scheme of YAG raw material

Table 1 The list of samples, YAG content and YAG increment in samples in depending of processing conditions (processing path) according to three-stage synthesis scheme (Fig. 1)

RM	The samples name	The processing path	The YAG phase content (%)	The YAG increment (%)
1	1a	24_T1	32	32
	1b	48_T1	63	63
	1c	72_T1	62	62
2	2a	24_T1 + IG + T2	50	18
	2b	48_T1 + IG + T2	79	16
	2b*	48_T1 + T2	63	1
3 A	3a	24_T1 + IG + T2 + IG + T3	91	41
	3b	48_T1 + IG + T2 + IG + T3	95	14
	3b*	48_T1 + T2 + IG + T3	93	30
3 B	3a-C	24_T1 + IG + T2 + IG + C + T3	94	44
	3b-C	48_T1 + IG + T2 + IG + C + T3	96	17
	3b*-C	48_T1 + T2 + IG + C + T3	94	31

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

High purity initial powders of Al_2O_3 (99.995%, Alchimica, Czech Republic) and Y_2O_3 (99.99%, Treibacher Industry, Austria) were chosen as commercially available materials widely used in preparation of raw materials for growing YAG single crystals.

2.2 Preparation

The preparation of YAG raw material was carried out by solid-state reaction method. Each of the investigated samples passed through the a preparatory process following the three-stage synthesis scheme presented in Fig. 1. The first synthesis stage includes the preliminary grinding (pre-milling) of the initial powders mixture and its calcination at 1150 °C during 24 h. The second and third stages comprise intermediate grinding (IG) procedure for 24 h followed by firing at 1250 °C and 1450 °C with a dwell time of 10 h.

The initial oxides Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 were weighed to match the YAG stoichiometric composition (62.5 mol% Al_2O_3 , 37.5 mol% Y_2O_3). Three individual batches (a, b, c) were prepared, differing by the pre-milling time (24 h, 48 h and 72 h), respectively. The pre-milling and intermediate grinding were carried out in the ball mill (polyethylene bottle) at the rate of 100 rpm. Ethanol was used as a solvent, and 99.99% pure Al_2O_3 balls ($\varnothing \approx 1$ cm) were used as a milling media. After each milling procedure, the powders were dried in the electronic furnace at 100 °C and sieved with 120 mesh. The list of samples, details of their mechanical and thermal treatment (TT), an appreciated YAG phase contents and YAG phase increments are summarized in Table 1 and Table 3. The last column shows in the difference between the YAG content in the current and the previous synthesis stage. During the last synthesis stage, the samples were fired as a powder and as compacts ("C") that were obtained by uniaxial pressing at 20 MPa ($40 \times 40 \times 32$ mm³). The sign "*" means the absence of IG in the second synthesis stage. All thermal treatments were carried out in the air in a muffle furnace with silite rods.

2.3 Characterization

The starting oxides Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 powders were characterized in terms of particle size (PS) and particle size distribution (PSD) using a particle size analyzer (Mastersizer 2000, Malvern, UK). The results are presented in Table 2 and Fig. 2, respectively. For individual measurements, aqueous suspensions of powders (weight of sample = 500 mg) were prepared in an ultrasonic bath and sonicated for 5 min.

The morphology and microstructure of raw powders and individual samples were investigated using scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL 7600F) equipped with EDXS detector Oxford X-Max 50 mm² using accelerating voltage of 15 kV. SEM-images of starting Al_2O_3 (a) and Y_2O_3 (b) powders are presented in Fig. 3.

The phase composition of the prepared samples was estimated after each firing using the X-ray powder diffraction analysis (Panalytical Empyrean DY1098, 45 kV accelerating voltage, CuK α radiation with $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$). Individual XRD patterns were recorded in the range of 2θ angle $10\text{--}80^\circ$. The diffraction patterns were evaluated using the software High-Score Plus (v.3.0.4, PAN Analytical, The Netherlands) with the COD 2023 database. The deviation for XRD measurements

Table 2 The results of PSA analysis of starting oxides

Powder	D10 (μm)	D50 (μm)	D90 (μm)
Y_2O_3	2.3	5.8	12.5
Al_2O_3	0.3	1.3	3.5

D10—quantile -lower decile, D50—quantile -median, D90—quantile -upper decile, Span—width of distribution

Fig. 2 Particle size distribution of initial powders

Fig. 3 SEM-images of initial Al_2O_3 a and Y_2O_3 b oxides

is $\pm 5\%$. The quantitative phase composition was estimated by the Rietveld refinement method with the precision of approximately $\pm 0.5\%$.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Starting materials characterization

Table 2 presents the results of the PS analysis conducted for the initial oxide powders. The parameters used in the analysis are also explained for better comprehension. D10, D50, and D90 values signify that 10 %, 50 %, and 90 % of the sample consist of particles smaller than the corresponding values. The analysis revealed that the powders contained particles of about ten micrometers in size, with the Al_2O_3 powder having smaller particles compared to the yttrium oxide powder. The span value was 1.569 and 1.750 for Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 , respectively, indicating satisfactory PSD of the initial powders. Figure 3 also provides a visual representation of the analysis results. Both powders showed a bimodal particle size distribution, with the particle size analysis curve of Al_2O_3 powder having a higher proportion of particles in the range of 0.3–6 μm and a smaller proportion in the range of 7.6–30.2 μm . In comparison, the Y_2O_3 powder had particles ranging from 0.4 to 1 μm and 1.2 to 22.9 μm , with the mean particle size being four times larger than the Al_2O_3 particles.

The research on the proposed YAG multi-stage synthesis process was divided into four stages. The first three research milestones (stages) are devoted to determining the effect of processing conditions (pre-milling time, presence or absence of IG) on the phase transformation in samples after each subsequent stage in accordance with the YAG synthesis three-stage scheme. The characteristic XRD-patterns for samples obtained in different research milestones with the pre-milling time of 48 h are shown in Fig. 4, and demonstrate the increase of YAG phase content with the each successive firing. However, in no case monophasic YAG was observed. Based on the study results of the three-stage YAG synthesis scheme, we proposed the fourth research milestone, devoted to investigation of the possibility of simplifying the process. The conditions of the TT and mechanical processing of samples and its approximate YAG phase content calculated by the Rietveld refinement method are presented in Table 1. Samples are marked according to the following principle: the letter corresponds to pre-milling time (a—24 h, b—48 h, c—72 h), the number—research milestone number; “C” indicates the compacted specimen, “*” sign points to the absence of IG in the 2nd synthesis stage. The control sample of YAG obtained by the classic (“one-stage”) synthesis scheme, which includes the ball-milling stage, presswork (pressing), and calcination at 1450 $^\circ\text{C}$, is named “4-C”.

3.2 The first research milestone (1150 $^\circ\text{C}$)

The primary objective in this stage is to determine the impact of pre-milling time on the phase composition of powder mixtures that undergo firing at 1150 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. An increase in the YAG content from 32 % to 63 % was registered for samples 1a and 1b ground for 24 and 48 h, respectively (Table 2). The garnet content in sample 1c did not change relative to sample 1b, that may indicate the same level of grinding for the powder mixtures ground for

Fig. 4 XRD-patterns of the powder mixtures pre-milled for 48 h and exposed to different mechanical and thermal treatment

Fig. 5 SEM-images of mixtures of Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 oxides after pre-milling for 24 h **a**, 48 h **b** and 72 h **c**

Fig. 6 The SEM images and distribution maps of Al and Y acquired via an EDSX of mixtures of Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 oxides after pre-milling for 24 h **a**, 48 h **b** and 72 h **c**

48 and 72 h. SEM studies of the powder microstructure confirmed this assumption. Figure 3 shows that the initial Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 powders quite strongly differ in terms of their average grain size parameter—about 0.3–1 μm and 5 μm , respectively. Despite this, they can be ground to a finer particle size in 48 h, as shown in Fig. 5 b, without significant changes when the exposure time is increased to 72 h (Fig. 5c). The larger particles of 2–3 μm in diameter seen in Fig. 5b, c are Y_2O_3 . At the same time, the elemental distribution study by the EDSX method showed sufficient homogenization already after 24 h of milling (Fig. 6a).

To sum up, the amount of time spent by pre-milling has a notable effect on the mixture homogeneity and PSD providing the increased YAG content after calcination. Based on the outcomes of SEM and XRD analysis of samples that have undergone different mechanical processes, we can conclude that extending the pre-milling time beyond 48 h is not effective. As a result, we have excluded powder samples milled for 72 h from further stages of the study.

3.3 The second research milestone (1250 °C)

In the second research milestone, we determined the influence of the IG factor on the YAG phase content increase in the samples after firing at 1250 °C for 10 h. The YAG increment was 18 % for the **2a** specimen and slightly less—13 % for the **2b** (see Table 1). The absence of IG in the second stage of the process for sample **2b*** led to a slight increment in the YAG phase, the recorded value of which lies within the measurement accuracy. A significant reduction of the SSR rate is attributed to a diffusion-limited process caused by the resulting diffuse layer consisting of intermediate products YAM, YAP, and YAG. This layer will induce a significant resistance to diffusion controlling the formation of the YAG phase, and a simple parabolic rate laws should be valid for each product layers growth in case of both simultaneous and associated growth [24]. For samples **2a** and **2b**, intermediate grinding apparently leads to the destruction of these layers, contributing to the acceleration of the YAG formation reaction in the second synthesis stage.

3.4 The third research milestone (1450 °C)

The complete synthesis process, including all three synthesis stages according to the scheme illustrated in Fig. 1 is considered at the third research milestone. The third stage of the YAG production process includes the grinding and firing at a temperature of 1450 °C for 10 h. For possible comparison of the results obtained in this work with sample **4-C**, prepared by the conventional single-stage scheme, some samples were fired in the form of compacts made by cold uniaxial pressing. Regardless of the TT mechanical treatment at the previous stages of the process, after firing at 1450 °C, for all powder samples **3a**, **3b*** and **3b**, the final YAG content was approximately the same—about 93 % ± 2 %, which lies within the range of the measurement error (Table 1, Sect. 3A). The influence of the molding step of the samples by cold uniaxial pressing antecedent to final firing on the increase in the YAG phase turned out to be insignificant, despite the increase in the powder grains contact area (Fig. 7). According to the results presented in Table 1 (Sect. 3B), it can be seen that the increase in the YAG phase content in comparison with fired powders was about 3 % and only for one of the three samples (**3a-C**).

As seen from Table 1, the YAG phase increase for samples **3a**, **3b*** and **3b** in the final process stage was 41 %, 31 %, and 14 %, respectively, with the last one having the highest intermediate garnet content of 79 %. Due to this, we can assume that the factor of high intermediate YAG content in sample **3b** caused a significant decrease in the YAG phase growth rate in the final stage of synthesis. If we consider the SSR conditions at the points of powder grain contacts, they will turn out to be the same for the samples **3b** and **3b***. Further firing should result in an equal increase in the YAG phase content, but this assumption was not confirmed by the experimental results. Consequently, the presence of various intermediate YAG contents in the samples under consideration is an active factor influencing the further course of the SSR. The investigations of the reacted mixture by SEM during the obtaining process showed partial sintering and grain enlargement up to the average size of 1.5–2.5 μm average size (Fig. 8).

To explain the results obtained at this research stage, we propose a simple model considering the conditions for a decrease or increase in the YAG phase increment, depending on the nature of redistribution nature of powder grains

Fig. 7 The estimate of samples molding by cold uniaxial pressing (20 MPa) influence on the YAG phase formation process

Fig. 8 The microstructure of **1b** sample **a** and **3b** sample **b**, after calcination at 1150 °C and 1450 °C, respectively

after intermediate grinding. After IG, new particle contacts of the initial and already formed compounds appear, and the reactivity of the mixture will depend on the YAG content and the redistribution of the remaining components over its volume. During the elements map distribution study (Fig. 9) of sample **3b**, despite the sufficient homogeneity, the local areas of the composition deviation from YAG stoichiometry scattered though the surface are observed, which confirms the above assumption, that the reaction slows down because of the contact of the phases incapable to react between themselves.

If the ground powder contains a sufficient amount of YAG, it can promote synthesis reactions (1), (2), and (3) to proceed at the same time as decomposition reactions (4) and (5). As a result, the rate of garnet formation decreases sharply.

Fig. 9 SEM micrographs of **3b** samples and distribution maps of Al and Y acquired by an EDXS **a**; the histogram of the cations ratio in the studied points for **3b b**

For experimental verification of the proposed model, sample **3b** with the lowest YAG phase growth rate was subjected to additional firing at a temperature of 1450 °C for 5 h. After such TT, no changes in the phase composition were registered within the measurement accuracy, which affirms the applicability of the presented model to explain the obtained results and for planning a multi-stage YAG synthesis process. Thus, the YAG content formed at the previous stages of the three-stage synthesis scheme is a factor limiting the number of stages in the obtaining process of the monophasic product. In this connection, we suggested the concept of “critical YAG concentration” with the value lying in the range of 60–80 %, the achievement of which before IG reduces the process efficiency.

3.5 The fourth research milestone (1150° + 1450 °C)

In order to improve the YAG synthesis process, we proposed a two-stage process consisting of the first and last stages of the three-stage synthesis scheme, supplemented by the sample pressing before the last firing. We determined the stages of the proposed process based on the results obtained during previous milestones. When choosing the conditions for the first stage, we considered that the high firing efficiency at 1150 °C ensured the high, but not critical YAG content for samples **1a** and **1c** (about 60 %), and the maximum YAG content was reached after firing at 1450 °C in the second step. Processing conditions and the XRD results of specimens prepared in the fourth research milestone are shown in Table 3. Sample **4-C**, obtained by the “conventional” (one-stage) scheme, was used as a reference sample when comparing the results. The processing conditions and YAG phase content for the preparation of samples **4a-C**, **4b-C**, and **4b*-C** in the first stage of the considered process was identical to samples **1a** and **1b** in the first research milestone were the same (see Table 1).

The study of phase analysis by XRD showed the presence of impurity phases of YAP and unreacted Al_2O_3 in samples **4a-C** and **4b*-C**, in contrast to **4b**, which appears monophasic (Fig. 10).

The YAG content resulting from the two-stage process was 90 %, 99 %, and 80 % for samples **4a-C**, **4b-C**, and **4b*-C**, respectively, and the phase increment was 58 %, 36 %, and 18 %. Sample **4a-C** showed the most significant increase in garnet content (58 %), than can be compared with the conventionally prepared **4-C** sample. However, it did not provide a monophasic product, probably because of the low YAG content (32 %) in the first processing stage or insufficient annealing time at 1450 °C.

The effect of IG on the two-stage synthesis process is clearly expressed when comparing samples **4b-C**, and **4b*-C**. Figure 11 demonstrates the YAG phase increment dynamics for both three-stage and two-stage processing schemes of mixtures milled for 24 h and 48 h, during each individual synthesis stage, i.e. over the given time at the certain temperature. When considering the first case, the negative effect of the absence of IG on the YAG increment in the second

Table 3 The YAG phase content in the samples obtained by the SSR method in accordance with the two-stage synthesis scheme, depending on the processing conditions

Research milestone	Samples name	The processing path	The YAG phase content (%)	The increment of YAG (%)
4	4a-C	24_T1 + IG + C + T3	90	58
	4b-C	48_T1 + IG + C + T3	99	36
	4b*-C	48_T1 + C + T3	80	17
	4-C	48_C + T3	58	58

Fig. 10 The XRD patterns of the samples obtained by the two-stage synthesis process

Fig. 11 The dynamics of YAG phase increment according to pre-milling time of batches for the three-stage synthesis process (a) and for two-stage synthesis process (b)

stage (for 48 h pre-milled samples), with sharply increasing in the 3rd stage was observed. Despite the small YAG phase increment for the 24 h pre-milled samples (black curve) in the first stage, in the 2nd and 3rd synthesis stages, it harshly increases, exceeding that one for 48 h pre-milled samples, herewith remaining unchanged (the curve has a constant slope) in both stages. The curve behavior of the 24 h pre-milled sample synthesized by two-stage scheme is almost the same as in a three-stage process, however, the final YAG content is lower here in the range of the measurement accuracy. In the case of pre-milling for 48 h under the same thermal treatment conditions and equal initial values of the YAG content (as a result of the 1st synthesis stage), carrying out the IG in the second stage of synthesis made it possible to obtain a monophasic product (99 %) resulting in a twofold increase in the YAG formation rate compared to the sample, obtained without IG (80 %).

The YAG phase content of 58 % in control **4-C** sample is comparable to 63 % for sample **1b**, which may indicate approximately the same time-averaged efficiency of 10 h firing at 1450 °C and 24 h calcination at 1150 °C. Therefore, in accordance with the literature data on the conventional one-stage process in the firing time interval of 5–10 h, the firing temperature of 1450 °C is insufficient to obtain a monophasic product [13].

4 Conclusions

The study of the SSR YAG synthesis features according to the multi-stage scheme using commercial micrometer-sized powders of yttrium and aluminum oxides showed higher efficiency than the conventional single-stage one. The hypothesis that grinding the partially reacted mixture accelerated YAG formation was experimentally confirmed, which implies

the destruction of the diffusion layers between the contacting powder grains and the reaction acceleration in the subsequent synthesis stage. We proposed the simple model of multi-stage synthesis, including the concept of the critical concentration of the product (YAG), the achievement of which in an intermediate process stage before grinding, limits the course of YAG synthesis reactions in subsequent process stages. According to the study results, the product's critical concentration in the penultimate stage of the process should not exceed 60 %. The presented simple model of the process with intermediate stages of thermal and mechanical treatment of powders mixtures requires a more detailed experimental study, which will be the subject of the following publication.

The proposed process for producing monophasic garnet does not require sophisticated equipment and makes it possible to reduce the final annealing temperature to 1450 °C. The study results can be useful in various fields connected with using of monophasic garnet powders and, in particular, in laboratories working on the crystal growth research.

The study of the thermodynamic and energetic characteristics of the oxide mixture at different stages of the YAG synthesis multi-stage process and the development of a way to achieve the maximum raw material density are interesting and promising directions for further research.

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Declarations

Competing interests The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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